

Risk Factors Associated with the Development of Anorectal Fistula after Drainage of an Anorectal Abscess

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anorectal abscess is a common surgical condition, and its main complication is anal fistula, which significantly affects quality of life.

Objective: To identify risk factors associated with anal fistula development after anorectal abscess drainage.

Material and methods: An observational, retrospective, analytical, and cross-sectional study was conducted in 215 patients treated between March 2022 and March 2024. Sociodemographic, clinical, metabolic, and therapeutic variables were analyzed. Bivariate analysis and multivariate binary logistic regression were performed to identify independent risk factors.

Results: A total of 193 patients (89.8%) developed anal fistula. In the multivariate analysis, spontaneous drainage was identified as the main independent risk factor (OR = 9.28; 95% CI: 3.61–23.87; $p < 0.001$). Body mass index was also significantly associated, showing a 13% increase in risk per additional unit (OR = 1.13; 95% CI: 1.01–1.27; $p = 0.045$).

Conclusions: Spontaneous drainage and increased body mass index are independent risk factors for anal fistula development after anorectal abscess drainage.

KEYWORDS: Anorectal abscess, anal fistula, risk factors, body mass index, surgical drainage

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I. INTRODUCTION

Anorectal abscess is a localized purulent collection within the perianal or perirectal tissues, most commonly resulting from obstruction and infection of the anal glands. Its most frequent etiology is cryptoglandular, and it represents one of the most common emergencies in coloproctology. The most relevant complication following abscess drainage is the development of an anorectal fistula, a chronic sequela that may occur in a variable proportion of cases, ranging from 15% to 60% according to different clinical series.¹⁻⁹

An anorectal fistula is an abnormal tract with fibrous walls that connects an infected anal gland to the perianal skin or the rectal lumen. Its formation entails a substantial clinical burden, including the need for multiple surgical interventions, the risk of fecal incontinence, work absenteeism, and deterioration in patients' quality of life.

Given its frequency and consequences, identifying the risk factors that predispose to its development is essential.¹⁰⁻¹⁷

Previous studies have suggested that variables such as male sex, advanced age, obesity, comorbidities (type 2 diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension), smoking, the use or non-use of antibiotics, and the type of abscess drainage (spontaneous or surgical) may be associated with the development of anorectal fistulas. However, the results reported in the literature have been heterogeneous, and many studies present methodological limitations or heterogeneous populations. Moreover, in the Mexican context, data regarding this association are scarce.¹⁸⁻²⁶

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

An observational, retrospective, analytical, cross-sectional study was conducted in patients diagnosed with anorectal abscess who were treated at the General Surgery and

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Coloproctology Department of the Hospital General Regional Orizaba No. 1 of the Mexican Institute of Social Security, during the period from March 2022 to March 2024.

Medical records of adult patients with a diagnosis of anorectal abscess who underwent some form of drainage and had follow-up in the outpatient coloproctology clinic were included. The study population comprised approximately 480 patients. With a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%, a sample size of 215 medical records was calculated, all of which were included in the final analysis.

Data were obtained directly from physical and electronic medical records using a data collection instrument specifically designed for the study. The information was coded and entered into a database for subsequent statistical analysis.

Descriptive statistics were performed using frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and means and standard deviations for continuous variables.

For bivariate analysis, the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was used, as appropriate, to compare categorical variables between groups with and without fistula development. Body mass index (BMI), analyzed as a continuous variable, was compared using the Student's t-test for independent samples.

Subsequently, a multivariate binary logistic regression model was constructed to identify independent risk factors associated with the development of anorectal fistula. Results were expressed as odds ratios (ORs), with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) and p-values. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value < 0.05.

III. RESULTS

The sample consisted of a total of 215 patients diagnosed with anorectal abscess who underwent drainage. Regarding age distribution, a predominance of the 46–70-year age group was observed, accounting for just over half of the cases, with 97 patients (50.7%). The 20–45-year age group represented 45.1% of the population (n = 109), while patients older than 70 years constituted a minority, comprising only 4.2% of the total (n = 9). With respect to sex, there was a marked predominance of males, with 164 patients (76.3%), compared with 51 females (23.7%).

In terms of body mass index (BMI), the largest proportion corresponded to 84 patients who were overweight (39.1%) and 52 with class I obesity (24.2%), followed by 17 patients with class II obesity (7.9%) and 17 with class III obesity (7.9%). Patients with normal weight represented only 18.1% of the sample (n = 39). Regarding comorbidities and habits, 16.7% of patients had a history of diabetes mellitus, 26.0% were smokers, and 38.1% reported alcohol consumption.

With respect to the type of drainage performed, the vast majority of cases involved spontaneous drainage, with 176 patients (81.9%), whereas only 39 cases (18.1%) underwent

surgical drainage. Concerning antibiotic use, 171 patients (79.5%) received antibiotics following drainage, while 44 patients (20.5%) did not. Finally, during follow-up, 193 patients (89.8%) developed an anorectal fistula, in contrast to 22 patients (10.2%) who did not present this complication.

TABLE 1. SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS

Variable	Frequency	%
20–45 years	97	45.1%
46–70 years	109	50.6%
>70 years	9	4.1%
Male	164	76.2%
Female	51	23.7%
BMI: Normal	39	18.1%
IMC: Overweight	84	39%
IMC: Obesity I	52	24.1%
IMC: Obesity II	17	7.9%
IMC: Obesity III	17	7.9%
Diabetes mellitus	36	16.7%
Smoking	56	26%
alcoholism	82	38.1%
Surgical drainage	39	18.1%
Spontaneous drainage	176	81.8%
Antibiotic therapy	171	79.5%
Without antibiotic therapy	44	20.4%

A bivariate analysis of the variables included in the study was performed in order to identify their association with the development of anorectal fistula. Statistical tests were selected according to the nature of each variable. Categorical variables with adequate expected frequencies were compared using the chi-square test (grouped age, sex, diabetes mellitus, smoking, type of drainage, and antibiotic use). In cases where low expected frequencies were present in any cell (as occurred with alcohol consumption and some BMI subgroups), Fisher's exact test was applied. For the continuous variable (body mass index expressed as mean ± standard deviation), mean values were compared between patients with and without fistula using the Student's t-test for independent samples.

TABLE 2. COMPARISON BETWEEN PATIENTS WITH AND WITHOUT ANORECTAL FISTULA

Variable	With fistula (n)	Without fistula (n)	p
20–45 years	84	13	0.244
46–70 years	102	7	0.1
>70 years	7	2	0.515
Male	147	17	1.0
Female	46	5	1.0
BMI	189	20	0.006

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Diabetes mellitus	31	5	0.623
Smoking	54	2	0.098
Alcoholism	82	0	<0.001
Surgical drainage	26	13	<0.001
Spontaneous drainage	167	9	<0.001
Antibiotic therapy	152	19	0.576

Statistically significant differences were observed in body mass index (BMI), as patients who developed a fistula had a higher mean BMI compared with those who did not develop this complication (32.0 ± 24.9 vs. 26.7 ± 3.2 ; $p = 0.006$), as shown in Table II.

Similarly, the type of drainage showed a differentiated pattern: patients who underwent spontaneous drainage more frequently progressed to fistula compared with those treated with surgical drainage ($p < 0.001$), as shown in Table II.

Alcohol consumption was also significantly associated, as it was documented exclusively in the group with fistula ($p < 0.001$), as shown in Table II.

In contrast, variables such as age (despite a trend in the 46–70-year age group; $p = 0.100$), sex, presence of diabetes mellitus, smoking, and antibiotic use did not show statistically significant differences between groups.

For the multivariate analysis, a binary logistic regression model was applied to identify independent risk factors associated with the development of anorectal fistula. In the adjusted model, patients of older age (>70 years) showed a significantly higher risk of developing a fistula compared with the reference group aged 20–45 years (OR = 4.33; 95% CI: 1.05–17.9; $p = 0.041$). Likewise, body mass index behaved as an independent risk factor: for each additional BMI unit, the probability of developing a fistula increased by 13% ($\beta = 0.118$; SE = 0.056; OR = 1.13; 95% CI: 1.01–1.27; $p = 0.045$).

The type of drainage showed a significant association with the development of anorectal fistula. Patients who underwent spontaneous drainage had a 5.33-fold higher probability of developing a fistula compared with those who underwent surgical drainage ($\beta = 1.674$; SE = 0.642; OR = 5.33; 95% CI: 1.56–18.21; $p = 0.006$). In contrast, sex, diabetes mellitus, smoking, alcohol consumption, and antibiotic use were not significantly associated with the development of anorectal fistula ($p > 0.05$).

Overall, the multivariate model indicates that advanced age (>70 years), increased BMI, and spontaneous drainage are independent risk factors associated with the development of anorectal fistula following abscess drainage.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the present study, which included 215 patients with a history of anorectal abscess, a high frequency of progression

to anorectal fistula was observed (89.8%). This proportion is higher than that reported by Särnman et al. in 2017 in the article “Perianal Abscess”, where the incidence of fistula following abscess ranged from 30% to 50%. This discrepancy may be explained by the characteristics of the population treated at our hospital, as well as by the high proportion of spontaneous drainage and the presence of risk factors such as overweight, obesity, and alcohol consumption.²⁷

Spontaneous drainage was identified as the main factor associated with fistula formation, with an odds ratio (OR) of 9.28. This finding is consistent with reports in the literature, which describe that formal surgical drainage reduces the risk of recurrence and fistulization compared with spontaneous or inadequate drainage. In the 2015 consensus of the Italian Society of Colorectal Surgery (Amato et al.), it is emphasized that early surgical drainage allows better evacuation of the abscess and reduces the persistence of infected crypts, thereby decreasing the likelihood of progression to fistula. In this study, the low proportion of surgical drainage (18.1%) reinforces the relevance of this factor.¹⁶

Another relevant finding was the association between body mass index (BMI) and the development of anorectal fistula, with a 13% increase in the probability of fistula development for each additional BMI unit. In an observational study including more than 1,200 patients, Ye et al. (2024), in “Restricted cubic spline model analysis of the association between anal fistula and anorectal abscess incidence and body mass index”, reported that overweight increased the risk (OR 1.35; 95% CI: 1.00–1.82; $p = 0.047$) and obesity tripled the risk (OR 3.44; 95% CI: 2.26–5.26; $p < 0.001$) of developing anorectal fistula or abscess. This supports the hypothesis that elevated BMI may act as a predisposing factor. Likewise, a study by Zhao et al. (2024), “Associations of Obesity with the Risk of Anal Fistula: A Mendelian Randomization Study”, using Mendelian randomization to estimate genetic causality, found that adiposity indicators such as BMI, body fat percentage, waist circumference, and waist-to-hip ratio have a positive causal effect on the risk of anorectal fistula ($p < 0.05$). Taken together, these findings strengthen the hypothesis that elevated BMI is not only associated with, but may also directly contribute to, the development of fistula.²⁸⁻²⁹

Alcohol consumption was present exclusively among patients who developed fistula (38.1%), which prevented calculation of an OR in the regression model. Nevertheless, previous studies, such as that by Lohsiriwat et al. in 2010 (“Incidence and factors influencing the development of fistula-in-ano after incision and drainage of perianal abscesses”), did not find a significant association between alcohol consumption and fistula formation after abscess drainage. This qualitative difference between our results and the existing evidence may reflect population-related factors, differences in the definition of “alcohol consumption,” or

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simply the limited sample size. However, it suggests that alcohol remains a clinically relevant factor that warrants further investigation in future studies with greater statistical power.³⁰

With regard to age, a significant association was observed in the group older than 70 years (OR = 4.33; 95% CI: 1.05–17.9; $p = 0.041$). This result is consistent with recent population-based evidence, such as the study by Sánchez-Haro et al. (2023), “Clinical characterization of patients with anal fistula during follow-up of anorectal abscess: a large population-based study”, in which older adult patients showed a significantly higher risk of progression from abscess to fistula. This finding suggests a possible relationship with the accumulation of comorbidities or delays in medical care among older age groups. Conversely, neither diabetes mellitus nor smoking showed a significant association in our cohort, which contrasts with the findings of Adamo et al. (2016), “Prevalence and recurrence rate of perianal abscess”, where diabetes was associated with a higher recurrence rate of abscesses and, consequently, a greater risk of fistulization. These differences may be explained by the relatively low prevalence of diabetes (16.7%) in our sample and by adequate metabolic control in some of these patients.^{31,32}

Antibiotic use did not show a significant impact on fistula prevention. This result is consistent with findings reported in clinical studies and international consensus statements, which indicate that adjunctive antibiotic therapy does not significantly reduce progression to fistula when adequate drainage is performed. In a prospective study, Sözen et al. (2011), “The role of antibiotics in the treatment of simple perianal abscesses”, concluded that antibiotic use does not decrease the incidence of subsequent fistula. Similarly, the 2015 consensus statement of the Italian Society of Colorectal Surgery (“Evaluation and management of perianal abscess and anal fistula”) emphasizes that antibiotics do not replace surgical drainage nor prevent fistulization. In our series, 79.5% of patients received antibiotics, which may have masked more subtle differences within specific subgroups.^{16,33}

V. CONCLUSIONS

It is established that the development of anorectal fistula following abscess drainage is significantly influenced by age, body mass index, and the type of intervention employed. The hypothesis proposed in this study is partially confirmed, as not all of the initially proposed factors were shown to have a direct influence.

The present study provides local clinical evidence that contributes to the understanding of factors influencing the evolution of anorectal abscess. Among its main strengths are the comprehensive characterization of the sample, the use of multivariate analysis, and the reinforcement of the clinical argument in favor of planned surgical drainage.

The limitations of this study include its retrospective design, the absence of data regarding the type of antibiotic used, and the lack of inclusion of anatomical variables of the abscess. These limitations should be considered in future research in order to achieve a more comprehensive model.

It is recommended to implement prevention and targeted follow-up strategies in patients with overweight or obesity presenting with anorectal abscess. Likewise, a planned surgical approach should be favored in these cases, and prospective studies including antibiotic type, anatomical location of the abscess, and long-term follow-up are suggested.

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